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Diffusion of Responsibility

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Abstract

Diffusion of responsibility and bystander effect have been investigated with sufficient empirical attention. All the same, there is not a-lot of review on the topic at the present time so that, this review pursued to set an examination for the literature on the topic of the diffusion of responsibility and bystander effect. In this section, I selected the Nazi trial and a random happening in a street to show the pervasiveness of the phenomenon of the diffusion of responsibility and bystander effect in daily life. Then, the latent causes of the diffusion of responsibility as the group size, self-awareness, and culture were explored. Lastly, I examined the phenomenon of the bystander effect, helping behavior, social loafing, and risk-taking behavior as the main effects of the diffusion of responsibility. This review presents a foundation for future researchers.

Keywords: *Diffusion of Responsibility, Bystander Effect.*

Introduction

In the late hours of the night in 1964 a young woman named Kitty.g. in New York city was murdered outside her house. Two weeks later, in the article which got published by “New York times” the title was like that:”38 people were the witness of the attack, but they refused to inform the cops to her aid. The Incuriosity of people have shocked the investigator.” The case was viral because of what happened:

Around 2a.m. Kitty was going to her house when an attacker man with a knife kept following her, she immediately ran to her house and screamed while the man was stabbing her body. One of the neighbors heard her and came to let the attacker leave her alone. Kitty was badly injured and she tried her best to return her house. After ten minutes, the attacker was back again, this time man raped and stabbed her to death, yet no one came to help her. Her death body was found by another neighbor later at that day.

Research has shown that for more than half an hour 38 respectable people heard the desperate cries for help or saw the attack, yet they refused to call the cops to her aid even though they used to have a good relationship. The question which got people thinking for a long time was that: Why?

All the neighbors said the same thing while they were interviewing someone would help her. The phenomenon of diffusion of responsibility is visible in different parts of daily life. People may notice that when in such a situation someone needs help, the more the peoples’ number, the less the people would be willing to help. Nowadays, people would think that people are turning more apathetic to each other even though understanding the pervasiveness of the phenomenon of diffusion of responsibility would help them to avoid being indifferent.

In the present review, two examples of diffusion of responsibility in a street and in a historical happening to show the impact of diffusion of responsibility in people’s daily life were explored. Then, the three causes of this phenomenon including group size, self-awareness, and culture were analyzed. Lastly, we propounded about the effects of the diffusion of responsibility to show its close connection with our daily life.

Pervasiveness of Diffusion of Responsibility

Diffusion of Responsibility in a Street

Imagine you are in Times Square while on a trip to New York City. As You are exploring the area and sightseeing, you see a woman who has fallen down, badly injured, and not able to get up.

Firstly, you look around and you notice other people around you and the woman, then you think that” okay most definitely someone have informed the emergency services or someone would help her.” Then you just shake your thoughts and continue sightseeing or whatever you were doing. This is what we call the diffusion of responsibility. Because of the existence of the others, that was easy to pass of the responsibility to take care of the woman to the other fellow bystander. As the research has made by two popular psychologists, 70 percent of the people who were solitary sought for a help, yet when they got paired with a gringo just 40 percent proposed help.

Diffusion of Responsibility in Nazi Trial

Diffusion of responsibility also includes positive behaviors, or the commission of actions, when an individual feels that he can pin the consequences of those behaviors on others rather than assume personal responsibility for them. This type of positive diffusion of responsibility constitutes the basis of the Nazi defense in the Nuremberg Trials. After the war, Allied powers-United States, Great Britain, France, and the Soviet Union- came together to form the International Military Tribunal. From 1945 to 1946, Nazi Germany leaders stood trial for crimes against peace, war crimes, crimes against humanity, and conspiracy to commit any of the foregoing crimes. The leaderships of this world war were 24men which were shown as the sinners of the war by the Supreme Court, but they weren’t the main characters, they were just the leaderships. The main characters which were Adolf Hitler, Heinrich Himmler, and Joseph Goebbels, since all these three men had committed suicide before the trials began so that the leaderships were believing that they are not the sinners and “they were just following the orders.”

Causes

Group Size

By evaluating the research from old to late, it’s prime that a multiplication in the group size is one of the most dominant factors that connects to the diffusion of responsibility. In the study, which made by Latané and Darley(1968) revealed the diffusion of responsibility in emergency situations. In an emergency, people in solitary acted faster than the people in groups. Additionally, there was a huge difference between the reaction of the participants. In an other study, which made by Latané and Dabbs(1972_1975) these experimenters dropped a pencil or some money in a lift in front of

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many people to see how people are going to react. The results showed that people are less likely to help when the number of individuals increased.

More over, in another study conducted by Wiesenhal(1983) a close connection between group size and diffusion of responsibility in a charity was revealed. The results showed that, people tend to donate more generously when they are solitary than they are in groups because they can easily pass off the responsibility to individuals who are present at the moment.

Self-Awareness

Self-awareness might be considered as a basis to explain group size and its connection with diffusion of responsibility. Wegner and Schaefer (1978) investigated mainly the responsibility to examine the function of self awareness in several helping scenarios. They put forward two hypotheses.

First, its ability to contribute to the diffusion of responsibility can be explained by reduced levels of self-awareness.

Second, out of previous studies, they concluded that increased responsibility focus can lead to an increase in self-awareness and, therefore, an increase in helping behavior.

Culture

Diffusion of responsibility appears differently under different cultural backgrounds. People who were grown up in collectivist cultures like republic of China (or many Asian countries), tend to show less diffusion of responsibility than the people from countries like United States. In another study (1989) they selected people from different cultures. A group was from China and the other group was from U.S. To waive the side effects they matched them in gender and age. Results showed that, people who were born and grown up in collectivist culture, work better in groups than individually in an emergency situation.

Effects

Bystander Effect in Children

This phenomenon also shows up in children either way. In 2007 researchers experimented to test that if children would try their best when doing a puzzling problem in a group. The findings showed that even younger children show social loafing. Afterwards, experimenters did a really close study to the pervious one in 2015. They set up three different situations for children to see if they're going to give a hand to the experimenter or not. The children were asked to join an activity in a

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room and do a-few paintings and then, the experimenter pretended that he spilt the hot water on himself and called for an aid. In first situation the kid were drawing with another individual. In the second position the kid was alone. In the third position to waive the side effects there was a paper which blocked two individuals so that the participants were the only one who could help. The results were similar to the previous one. When the participant was the only one who could help, the phenomenon of diffusion of responsibility didn't show up.

Helping Behavior

Latané and Darley (1968) made a research to show that diffusion of responsibility is not determined by how many people are involved and it's all about how many people are able to help the victim. These two psychologists made a situation to see that what would the participants do when they were not able to see or help the victim. For that, they selected participants from college students with the age range of 19 to 20. They were told to be in an ESTP test (Extraverted, Sensing, Thinking, Perceiving test) and not able to help their classmates. The main test was much different. The experimenter put a "victim" which was a recorded voice that represented a person who is in pain and the "participant" as a bystander. The bystander was asked to act in three different levels: no big deal, someone may get hurts, and serious emergency. They put the bystander in another building to waive the side effects. The results showed that when the bystander was not able to help, the diffusion of responsibility didn't show up.

Social Loafing

There is an expression between English people "many hands make light the work." A researcher named Max Ringelmann (1986) made a study to prove that it's not always true. In his study, he asked one group of individuals to pull the ropes all together and the other group to do it in individuals. The results shocked him "people tend to work better and put more effort individually than when they get paired or in a group". It can be concluded that people feel less responsible when they are in a group, so the diffusion of responsibility is in the maximum level.

Risk-Taking Behavior

Diffusion of responsibility also affects risk taking behavior. In a study, the researchers brought 12 individuals and they were asked to make a decision between two options, one of them comprising risk than the other one, yet it presented a better award. Then, experimenters divided them in groups of 6. Later on, they had to choose between two options with their group mates. The results showed that, people tend to make riskier decision in groups than the individual. To sum up, in groups, the personal responsibility got diffused and led to some risk taking behaviors. This essay was a review of effects, causes, and examples on diffusion of responsibility although there were a lot of limitations such as very limited number of related studies.

Conclusion

In this review, the researcher took up this topic due to its prevalence in everyday life, causes, and effects on human behavior. It showed that diffusion of responsibility plays an important role in life especially, in public circumstances. Future investigations could focus more on the implication based on the diffusion of responsibility.

People would get more information about this phenomenon and avoid it. Furthermore, the factor of culture plays a significant role in people's behavior the way that people would introduce helping each other as a main positive character in their culture to make the effect of diffusion of responsibility less than ever.

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